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The Challenges of Cybercrime in Nigeria: An Overview

¹Onuora, A. C., ²Uche, D. C., ³Ogbunude, F. O., ⁴Uwazuruike, F. O.

¹aconuora@akanuibiampoly.edu.ng, ²uchedan2007@yahoo.com,
³okechukwufestus91@gmail.com, ⁴faustygrace11@gmail.com

^{1,2,3,4} Department of Computer Science,

Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic Unwana

Abstract

Cybercrime involves using computers and Internet by individuals to commit crime. Cyber terrorism, identity theft and spam are identified as types of cybercrimes. The study identified some of the causes of cybercrimes to include urbanization, unemployment and weak implementation of cybercrime laws. The effects of cybercrimes on organizations, the society and the country in general include reducing the competitive edge of organizations, waste of production time and damage to the image of the country. With Nigeria venturing into cashless society, there is a need for cybercrimes menace to be minimized if not completely eradicated. This paper x-rayed various types of cybercrimes and what motivate individuals into indulging in such crimes. Firms should ensure that their IT infrastructures like Networks and computer systems are properly secured. Government should ensure that cybercrime laws are formulated and strictly adhered to and individuals should observe simple rules by ensuring antivirus protection on their computer systems.

Keywords: *Crime, Cybercrime, Cyber-criminal, Internet, Network, Security.* .

1.0 Introduction

The concept of cybercrime is historic and dates back with the advent of information and communication technology (Legislative and Government Relations Unit, 2015). Massive digitalization and unprecedented interconnectivity provided by the internet has been a windfall to people from all sphere of life including students, lecturers, doctors, architects, teachers, lawyers, businessmen and criminals.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) systems are now as basic to our lives as water and electricity. Many individuals, corporate organizations and government agencies depend on ICT and computer networks to perform simple as well as complex tasks – from

social networking and research to business and commerce. However, the cyberspace is increasingly becoming vulnerable as many businesses, agencies and individuals are being swindled by cyber criminals not only within the country but around the world.

Cyber Crime is a frequently used word by individuals in our contemporary Society. To understand the true meaning of cybercrime, there is the need to understand the slit meaning of Cyber and Crime. The term “*Cyber*” is a prefix used to describe an idea as part of the computer and Information age and “*Crime*” can be described as any activity that contravenes legal procedure mostly performed by individuals with a criminal motive. Cybercrimes are defined as: “Offences that are committed against individuals or groups of individuals with a criminal motive to intentionally harm the reputation of the victim or cause physical or mental harm to the victim directly or indirectly, using modern telecommunication networks such as Internet (Chat rooms, emails, notice boards and groups) and mobile phones” (Halder & Jaishankar 2011).

Cybercrime, as most people are already aware, refers to those criminal acts such as identity theft and bank frauds facilitated through the use of the internet. But as most Nigerians also know, to our collective shame, our country is often cited as a breeding ground for many of these nefarious practices because of the activities of some of our citizens. In the last few years, many criminal elements in Nigeria have been using these modern telecommunication networks such as the internet and mobile phones to commit all manner of crimes that portrays a bad image for the nation globally. Such crimes may threaten a nation’s security and financial health. Cybercrime can simply be said to be a crime carried out with the aid of Information and communication technology (ICT) tools.

Indeed, there is an upsurge of cybercrime in Nigeria. The country is ranked third in global internet crime after the United States of America and United Kingdom while 7.5 per cent of the world’s hackers are said to be Nigerians (Thisday, 2016). Committed mostly by the young, often called “Yahoo” boys, a precursor of the infamous ‘419’ email scammers, the fraudsters are increasingly taking advantage of the rise in online transactions, electronic shopping, e-commerce and the electronic messaging systems to engage in heinous crime.

2.0 Literature Review

According to Vladimir (2005) internet is a global network which unites millions of computer located in different countries and open broad opportunities to obtain and exchange information but it is now been used for criminal purposes due to the economic factors. Nigeria a third world country is faced with so many economic challenges such as poverty, corruption, unemployment amongst others, thereby, making this crime thrive.

However, it will be inconclusive to base it only on economic challenge as the cause of cyber-crime in Nigeria. Internet is the most technologically advanced medium of interaction. It is the information revolution that has turned the world into a global village.

As a result of this value, it is assumed that internet usage in Nigeria is growing due to increasing availability of broadband connections and by observation, a decrease in subscription fee. This observed increase of internet users in Nigeria has made the internet a popular medium of communication and interaction as well as forum for online enterprises, such as, internet service provision (ISP), cyber cafes and cybercrime which was described by Ayantokun (2006) as all unlawful activities involving computer and internet.

The internet services have reduced the world into a global village which makes it look as if everybody is in the same place at a particular point in time, aside from the fact that the internet has made communication to be easier and faster. A lot of other transactions are consummated at the speed of lightening. Oyewole and Obeta (2002), state that the internet is the inter connection of computer across the world thereby creating unlimited opportunities for mankind. According to Ehimen and Bola (2009), the internet has created a geometric growth and accelerated windows of opportunities for businesses and the removal of economic barriers hitherto faced by nations of the world. Considering these limitless advantages of the internet, one can easily subscribe to the fact that it is an important tool for national development in a developing country like Nigeria.

McConnel (2000), argued that cybercrimes differ from most terrestrial crimes in four ways which are: They are easy to learn; they require few resources relative to the potential damage caused; they can be committed in a jurisdiction without being physically present and they are often not clearly illegal. As such, cybercrime has become one of the major security issues for law enforcement agencies and the world in general.

According to a publication by Economic and Other Financial Crime Commission in Nigeria named Zero Tolerance (2006), stated that a retired civil servant with two (2) other accomplices defrauded a German citizen named Klaus Wagner a sum of USD 1, 714,080 through the internet. A 2007 internet crime report listed Nigeria third in terms of online crime activity and the prevalence of cybercrime among a sizeable number of young Nigerians (Sesan, 2010).

Ribadu (2007), stated that the prominent forms of cybercrime in Nigeria are cloning of websites, false representations, internet purchase and other e – commerce kinds of fraud. Olugbodi (2010), opined that the most prevalent forms of cybercrime are website cloning, financial fraud, identity theft, credit card theft, cyber theft, cyber harassment, fraudulent electronic mails, cyber laundering and virus / worms / Trojans.

2.1 Causes of Cyber Crime in the Nigeria.

Young people in Nigeria encompass a larger percentage of people seen in cybercafés perpetrating the act internet fraud and cyber pornography. This is characterized by a lot causes we are going to look at.

a. Unemployment:

Cybercrime can be associated with high rate of unemployment, harsh economic conditions, and poor educational system. According to the Nigerian National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria is saddled with almost 20 million unemployed people, with about 2 million new entrants usually graduated into the dispirited realm of unemployment yearly. This clearly reveals that a lot of youths are not employed. There is an adage that says “an idle mind is the devils workshop”; as such most of our youth will use their time and knowledge as a platform for their criminal activity, in order to improve their livelihood and to make ends meet. Government and private sectors should create job opportunities for youths graduating from higher institution yearly as to prevent them from engaging in cybercrime which usually presents itself as a quick and lucrative enterprise.

b. Urbanization:

Urbanization is one of the causes of Cybercrime in Nigeria; it is the massive movement of people from rural settlement to Cites. According to Ajaero and Onokala (2013), urbanization

is looked at as the massive physical growth of urban areas as a result of rural migration in search for a better life. This result in a heavy competition amongst the growing populace more especially the elites, as such the elites find it lucrative to invest in the crime of cyber because it is a business that requires less capital to invest and they are popularly called “Yahoo Boys”. Meke (2012), in his article “Urbanization and cybercrime in Nigeria” reiterated urbanization as one of the major causes of cybercrime in Nigeria and Urbanization will be beneficial if and only if good jobs can be created in the cities where population growth is increasing, in his article, he emphasized that urbanization without crime is really impossible. As such the elites amongst them find it lucrative to invest in the cybercrime because it is a business that requires less capital.

c. Weak Implementation of Cyber Crime Laws and Inadequate Equipped Law Agencies:

The Nigerian legislation must implement strict laws regarding cyber criminals and when criminal offences occur, perpetrators must be punished for the crime they’ve committed because cybercrime reduces the nation’s competitive edge, failure to prosecute, cyber criminals, can take advantage of the weak gaps in the existing penal proceedings. Weak / fragile laws regarding cyber criminals exist in Nigeria, unlike in the real world were criminals such as armed robbers are treated with maximum penalties. Unfortunate the nation is not well equipped with sophisticated hardware to track down the virtual forensic criminals. Laura (2012) stated that “African countries have been criticized for dealing inadequately with cybercrime as their law enforcement agencies are inadequately equipped in terms of personnel, intelligence and infrastructure, and the private sector is also lagging behind in curbing cybercrime” Nigeria is not an exception to this rule. Furthermore, it is therefore paramount that the nation’s legislation should ensure proper implementation of laws against cybercrime where cyber criminals are prosecuted and convicted if found guilty.

d. Quest for Wealth:

Another cause of cybercrime in Nigeria is quest for wealth, there exist a large gap between the rich and the average, as such many strive to level up using the quickest means possible, since for any business to thrive well, the rate of return in the investment must be growing at a geometric rate with a minimal risk. Most cyber criminals require less investment and a conducive environment. Nigeria is such an environment and many cyber criminals take advantage of that.

e. Negative Role Models:

Youths are mirrors of the society, but it is quite unfortunate how parents neglect their rightful duties. Meke (2012) remarked that today many parents transmits crime values to their wards, via socialization as if it a socio cultural values which ought to be transmitted to the younger generation. In addition, the high level of Cybercrimes patronage in Nigeria is one of the reasons why the crimes are seen as a norm in our society. No thanks to OluMaintain’s “yahoos” album, D’banj’s “Mobolowon”, and Kelly Handsome’s “Maga don pay” and a host of others in the entertainment and fashion industries who label their designs yahoo – shirts, signifying the style and taste of ‘young money bags’ with high taste and preference for expensive clothes and accessories. Imagine a situation where the child supplies the father with vital information to wreck individual’s banks account using the computer system, while the mother impersonates the account holder/owner at the bank. If this culture is imbibed among the younger generations most of them will see no wrong in cybercrime practices.

3.0 Forms of Cybercrimes

Maitanmi and Ogunlere (2013), outlined the various forms of cybercrime exhibited in Nigeria; they include;

3.1 Yahoo Attack: Also called 419 because section 419 of the Nigerian criminal code has a law against such offenders. It is characterized by using e-mail addresses obtained from the Internet access points using e-mail address harvesting applications (web spiders or e-mail extractor). These tools can automatically retrieve e-mail addresses from web pages. Nigerian fraud letters join the warning of impersonation scam with a variation of an advance fee technique in which an e-mail from Nigeria offers the recipient the chance to share a percentage of a huge amount of money that the author, a self-proclaimed government official, is trying to siphon out of the country.

3.2 Hacking: Here, Nigerian hackers are engaged in brainstorming sessions at trying to break security codes for e-commerce, funds point cards and e-marketing product sites.

3.3 Software Piracy: Piracy involves the unlawful reproduction and sharing of applications software, games, movies /videos and audios.

3.4 Pornography: Pornography covers all types“ photography, films and videotapes with varying degrees of sexual contents. The Internet has provided a free market for this crime as so many pornographic sites are now all over the net. This is one of the most popular cybercrimes in Nigerian academic institutions.

3.5 Credit Card or ATM Fraud: Credit card or ATM numbers can be stolen by hackers when users type the credit card number into the Internet page of the seller for online transaction or when withdrawing money using ATM card. The hackers can abuse this card by impersonating the credit card holder.

3.6 Denial of Service Attack: This is an act by the fraudster who floods the bandwidth of the victim’s system or fills his e-mail inbox with junk mails depriving him of the services he is entitled to access or supply.

3.7 Internet Relay Chat (IRC) Crime: IRC servers have chat rooms in which people from anywhere in the world can come together and chat with each other. Criminals use it for meeting co-conspirators. Hackers use it for discussing their exploits and sharing the techniques.

3.8 Virus Dissemination: A virus is a computer program that infects files, frequently executable programs, by inserting a duplication of itself into the file. There are different types of virus and each type requires human participation (usually unaware) of their spread.

3.9 Phishing: Phishing refers to cloning product and e-commerce web pages in order to dupe unsuspecting users. This is a technologically advanced scam that often uses spontaneous mails to trick people into disclosing their financial and/or personal data.

3.10 Cyber Plagiarism: This is the act of stealing peoples“ ideas through the Internet public domains. This is very common in academic institutions as students and lecturers alike use it to steal other people’s ideas and publish them as their own original work.

3.11 Spoofing: To have one computer on a network to act like another computer, usually one with exceptional access rights, so as to gain access to the other systems on the network.

3.12 Cyber Stalking: The fraudster follows the victim by distributing mails and entering the chat rooms frequently.

3.13 Cyber Defamation: The fraudster sends e-mails containing defamatory content to people related to the victim or posts it on a website.

3.14 Salami Attack: Salami assaults are flamboyant economic scams or exploits against confidentiality by comprehensive data gathering.

3.15 Cyber Terrorism: According to the U.S. Federal Bureau of Investigation, cyber terrorism is any premeditated, politically motivated attack against information, computer systems, computer programs, and data which results in violence against non-combatant targets by sub-national groups or clandestine agents (searchsecurity.techtarget.com [10]).

3.16 Others: Other cybercrimes not mentioned above are;

- a. Offences against critical national information infrastructure
- b. Intercepting electronic messages, emails, electronic money transfers
- c. Willful misdirection of electronic messages
- d. Unlawful interceptions
- e. Unauthorized modification of computer system, network data and system interference
- f. Electronic signature
- g. Fraudulent issuance of e-instruction
- h. Reporting of cyber threats
- i. Identity theft and impersonation
- j. Racists and xenophobic offences
- k. Attempt, conspiracy, aiding and abetting
- l. Importation and fabrication of e-tools
- m. Breach of confidence by service providers
- n. Manipulation of ATM/POS Terminals
- o. Employees responsibility
- p. Phishing, spamming and spreading of computer virus
- q. Electronic card related fraud
- r. Use of fraudulent device or attached e-mails and websites

4.0 Cyber Crime Act in Nigeria

The internet creates unlimited opportunities for commercial, social and educational activities. However, it has introduced its own peculiar risk that poses danger to the economy. The danger could affect many sectors of the society and put the development of the country into peril. Some of these possible adverse effects could include the destruction of the country's image both at home and abroad, insecurity of both life and properties, fear of doing business with Nigerian's citizen, economic loss of spending substantial amount of money on the prevention and control of cyber crime amongst others. The draft local legislation on electronic crimes, telecommunications and postal offences decree of 1995 define cybercrime as:

... Any person who, inter alia, engages in computer fraud or does anything to fake payments, whether or not the payment is credited to the account of an operator or the account of the subscriber, is guilty of an offence.

At the 10th U.N conference on the punishment of offenders, cybercrime was broken into two categories and thus defined as:

In a narrow sense, as any illegal behavior directed by means of electronic operations that target the security of computer system and data processed by them; and

In a broader sense, as any illegal behavior committed by means of or in relation to a computer system or network including such crimes as illegal possession and offering or distributing information by means of a computer system or network.

Computer crime, or cybercrime, is any crime that involves a computer and a network. The computer may have been used in the commission of a crime, or it may be the target. Net crime is criminal exploitation of the Internet, inherently a cybercrime. Cybercrime uses the unique features of the Net - sending of e-mail in seconds, speedy publication/ dissemination of information through the web to anyone on the planet. Computer attacks can be generated by criminals from anywhere in the world, and executed in other areas, irrespective of geographical location. Often, these criminal activities can be faster, easier and more damaging with the use of the Internet.

Cybercrimes in an Interconnected World have become pervasive and require immediate legislation. These include:

- All crimes imaginable offline that can be achieved with the use of computer networks as a tool
- Threats to lives and properties
- Disruption of critical services
- Terrorism and economic sabotage
- Propaganda
- Theft of information (identity & credit card theft)

The Nigerian Situation in relation to cyber activities concentrate efforts and attention on E-government services, payment platform for e-Commerce, ATM Machines, Electronic Activities of the NSE, Cashless banking services and Nigerian Electronic Identification system which include among others, the INEC card reader system.

The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) reported in 2015 that 70 per cent of attempted or successful fraud/forgery cases in the Nigerian banking system were perpetrated via the electronic channels. Between 2000 and 2013, banks in the country lost N159 billion to electronic frauds and cybercrime. In 2014, bank customers lost about N6 billion in Nigeria while in South Africa, the loss amounted to about N8 billion. Indeed, security experts said during the 2016 Cybersecurity Awareness Month in Lagos that financial losses to cybercrime may rise to \$6 trillion globally by 2021 (Thisday, 2016).

Earlier this year, Adebayo Shittu, Minister of Communications, spoke about the rate of cyber related offences such as fraudulent financial transactions and child kidnapping, facilitated through internet communications has increased in recent years. “If African leaders failed to address this threat, there will be negative impacts on economic growth, foreign investment and security,” said Shittu. “An effective response to cybercrimes requires a robust network security including appropriate network architecture and software, use of encryption, data protection legislation, information security standards and other tools of threat protection and detection.”

In 2015, the Cybercrimes Act was passed into law to address the challenges. The law criminalizes a variety of offences – from ATM card skimming to identity theft. It imposes, for instance, seven years imprisonment for offenders of all kinds and additional seven years for online crimes that result in physical harm, and life imprisonment for those that lead to death. But like almost every law in the country, there is the problem of enforcement. The “yahoo boys” still daily throng cybercafé premises to “transact” their business with the owners looking away. Yet the law criminalizes internet café owners who allow their premises to be used to commit online crimes.

In response to the apparent failure of the law to address the growing challenge, the minister canvassed the need to improve the capacity of relevant ICT and cyberspace stakeholders for the training and support of cyber security officials and the sharing of cyber security best practice from across the globe. These are in addition to building the capacity of local law enforcement. The time to do that is now.

5.0 The Imperatives for Nigeria

Since the loss suffered by consumers and investors creates serious credibility and image problems, many countries develop strategies for preventing, detecting and containing the threats associated with cybercrime. While it is acknowledged that greed is a major factor motivating most victims, what about the image created for many who never respond?

How is the nation fighting cybercrime? It's interesting that there is quite a lot of talk about fighting cybercrime. But what are the efforts? And how effective are they? Since there is an awareness of the menace it poses to society, what have been the sincere and meaningful efforts to fight cybercrime?

The significance of cyber legislation cannot be overemphasized in our contemporary Nigerian society. As outlined below, the imperativeness of cyber legislation in Nigeria could be viewed from the following perspectives:

- Establishment of Legal and Regulatory Framework
- Establishment of Institutional Framework for coordination and implementation;

- Standards and Regulations;
- Capacity Building
- Compliance & Enforcement;
- Emergency Response & Readiness;
- Public enlightenment
- International Cooperation and Institutional Framework.

6.0 Challenges

There exist serious challenges against the efforts both at the National and International level to fight against Cybercrime. However, Nigeria is confronted with challenges such as:

- The unending cyber battles (supremacy disagreements) among law enforcement, intelligence and security agencies;
- Lack of integration between the public and private sector in fighting against cybercrime.
- Inadequacy in the policy option that deals with the issues of surveillance.

7.0 Recommendations

There is to holistic approach to eradicating the menace of cybercrime in our society. As the use of technology increases day by day, crime committed using technology also increases. All stakeholders in Nigeria should put their heads together to minimizing cybercrime in Nigeria. This will not only eliminated our country from the top three ranked country where cybercrime flourish but will attract investors from Africa and the world at large thereby improving our economy. This paper recommends the following measures to all stakeholders in other to reduce cybercrime. They are

- Capacity building for all.
- Cooperation between actors (Private or Public)
- Establishment of Institutional framework for coordinating cyber security efforts
- Enactment of related Bills to strengthen the cyber security framework
- Installation of antivirus and anti-malware on computers.
- Securing networks with firewalls
- Sensitization of the public on how cybercrime is perpetrated and how it can be averted.
- Providing jobs for the unemployed.

- Create a security-aware culture involving the public, the ISPs, cybercafés, Network Providers, government, security agencies and Internet users
- Parents should monitor closely and possibly manage their children’s use of the Internet in order to minimize cyber-crime cases.

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